

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms Anjitha P V. bearing USN 6SU21OP001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/ Anjua D. bearing USN 6SU21OP002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/MsANUSREE P P bearing USN 6SU21OP003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/MsARCHA D BINU bearing USN 6SU21OP004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BENITA ABEY bearing USN 6SU21OP005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BHAVANA K V bearing USN 6SU21OP006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARSHINA KUNHAMMED V bearing USN 6SU21OP007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsHIBA FATHIMA K bearing USN 6SU21OP008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JASMY M SEBASTIAN bearing USN 6SU21OP009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsNANDANA BAIJU bearing USN 6SU21OP010has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre,mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSOORYA P bearing USN 6SU21OP011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSUHANA THASNIM P V bearing USN 6SU21OP012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms THEERTHA V bearing USN 6SU21OP013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms TUSHITH YASHWANTH SHETTY bearing USN 6SU21OP014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VARSHA K bearing USN 6SU21OP015 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FIDA FATHIMA bearing USN 6SU21OP016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Institute of medical science and research centre, mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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